

Urban Conservation Session Report

by the chair, Paul Meurs

It is tempting to start the session on urban conservation with some observations on Brasília, our host city and also one of the best and most complete examples of the Modern City in the world. Its historic value is out of discussion. The city also marks an important moment in the Brazilian history and embodies the quest for a national destiny and identity. Before the *Plano Piloto* was completely realized, the city was already included on the World Heritage List of UNESCO. Even though this recognition is obvious, the question how Brasília should be prepared for the future has many answers.

What actually makes up the quality of the city, or even better: what can be dismissed? How can changes occur without damaging the concept?

One can say that the essence of Brasília lies in the original buildings or in the zoning regulations that came along with the *Plano Piloto*. Another option is to consider the un-built spaces of the green areas and the surrounding landscapes as crucial for the preservation of the concept. A fourth possibility may be to redesign the city completely, for instance by preserving certain areas, like the *Superquadras*, and re-inventing other parts of the city, like the city-core which can improve by mixing uses (to start in this terrible hotel c.q. prostitution sector) and caring about the faith of pedestrians. Eventually, the challenge to prepare Brasília for the 21st century can also be considered in a much broader scale, by looking at the real city that spread out even beyond the limits of the Federal District, with all its satellites and dynamics, and picture the *Plano Piloto* as one of the pieces of a regional metropolitan puzzle.

The debate on the future of Brasília has nothing to do with the question if the project was a success; the city is as real as Paris, Rome or New York. Yet there is something that makes Brasília unique. The city is, in certain ways, a manifest, a symbol of rapture with urban traditions (even if Costa compared his design with certain parts of Paris and Beijing). The challenge of today's planners is to find ways of continuity in use and physical appearance, respecting Brasília as 'manifest' of the Modern Movement, and at the same time adjusting its environment to the conditions of a postmodern society, to the dynamic Brazilian reality.

In Brasília, the tension between continuity and change is brought to an extreme, and it is our task as planners and architects to deal with this kind of tension. No matter how much we respect Costa's magnificent *Plano*

Piloto - Brasília is a city that has to be re-invented again and again, to adjust it to changes within the Brazilian society and to the strong dynamics of the Federal District in particular. Poor planners of Brasília – their task seems to be impossible and unique, as unique as the city of Brasília itself.

At a more modest scale, many cities and countries face similar dilemmas of how to deal with continuity and change in a modernist urban environment. Many of these cases are less complex in the size of the modern intervention and the speed of the development, but by far more complex because they bear the mark of a century-long history of continuity and change. Five of these experiences will be presented and discussed in the session on urban conversation: Boston, Brussels, Dublin, Lübeck and the cities of constructivism in the Russian provinces. A paper on Mussolini's Rome will be included in the proceedings.

The Modern Movement helped shaping many cities throughout the world, all through the 20th century. In some cases, like in Boston, Brussels or Dublin, these innovations meant a certain tension with the existing urban fabric. Unlike the Plan Voisin of Le Corbusier for Paris, these cases also showed respect for the traditional city, as can be seen in Boston: the old city stayed almost intact, as the renewal focused on former rail and road constructions. In other cases, the planners could design on a tabula rasa: Lübeck had to be reconstructed after the city was bombed during World War II, and the Soviets planned numerous new towns shortly after the revolution in 1917. Nowadays, all these modernist schemes need certain re-adjustments: the towns gain new uses, need densification and mingled functions; the buildings might face repairs and the urban context brings about new raptures or continuities. How does the modernistic urban plans meet the changing circumstances? Should the cities be frozen in their modern features like Brasília? Or should the clock be turned backwards, as seems to be the tendency in Belgium, according to Sarah Moutury in her abstract on the skyscrapers of Brussels. Perhaps there is a third option in which the traditional and the modernistic cities can harmoniously coexist and melt together in brand-new urban schemes of the 21st century? The session on Urban Conversation will present the cases and try to discuss if any general remarks on how to 'overcome' or 're-enforce' the Modern City and modernism in the Historic City.